

1_Notebook_analysis

May 5, 2022

1 Notebook 1: Data analysis

supporting the manuscript: **Sensitivity of evapotranspiration and seepage to elevated atmospheric CO_2 from lysimeter experiments in a montane grassland**

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1.0.1 The supporting Notebook is structured as follows.

1. Import observation data
2. Compute simple statistics and plot:
 - Meteorological data used for the analysis plot
 - Annual change in soil water fluxes between the ambient lysimeter (L_{amb}) and the the eCO_2 lysimeter (L_{eCO_2})
 - Change in soil water fluxes between the vegetation period in L_{amb} and L_{eCO_2}
3. Analyze the Effects of elevated CO_2 on:
 - Evapotranspiration (ET)
 - Leaf area index (LAI)
4. Estimate stomatal resistance (r_l) for each lysimeter
5. Calibrate/parameterize the CO_2 dependent stomatal resistance model

The analysis is conducted on the ambient (reference) lysimeter (L_{amb}) and the CO_2 enriched lysimeter (L_{eCO_2}). In some occasions, **L0** stands for ambient contions and **L2** for elevated CO_2 .

```
[1]: # import needed packages
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

from scipy import stats
import datetime
import pylab

from spotpy.objectivefunctions import rmse, rsquared, kge
from lmfit import (Model, Parameters, fit_report,
                  minimize, conf_interval,
                  Minimizer, printfuncs,)

import pyet
from statsmodels.stats.stattools import durbin_watson
```

```
from utils import *  
  
pyet.show_versions()
```

```
Python version: 3.8.11 (default, Aug 6 2021, 09:57:55) [MSC v.1916 64 bit  
(AMD64)]  
Numpy version: 1.20.3  
Scipy version: 1.7.3  
Pandas version: 1.4.1  
Matplotlib version: 3.5.1  
Pyet version: 1.1.0b
```

```
[2]: # edit default values for plots  
params = {  
    "font.family": "Arial",  
    "legend.fontsize": "8",  
    "patch.linewidth": "10",  
    "lines.linewidth": "0.4",  
    "axes.labelsize": "6",  
    "axes.titlesize": "12",  
    "xtick.labelsize": "6",  
    "ytick.labelsize": "6",  
    "xtick.major.size": "2",  
    "ytick.major.size": "2",  
    "xtick.major.width": "0.3",  
    "ytick.major.width": "0.3",  
    "xtick.major.pad": "2",  
    "ytick.major.pad": "2",  
    "xtick.direction": "in",  
    "ytick.direction": "in",  
    "figure.subplot.wspace": "0.1",  
    "axes.labelpad": "1",  
    "axes.titlepad": "8",  
    "axes.linewidth": "0.4",  
    "xtick.minor.size": "1.5",  
    "xtick.minor.width": "0.15",  
    "hatch.linewidth": "0.2",  
}  
pylab.rcParams.update(params)
```

2 1. Import data

```
[3]: meteo = pd.read_csv("data\meteo_d_2015_2020.csv", index_col=0, parse_dates=True)  
meteo.describe()
```

```
[3]:
```

	Tmean_[C]	Tmax_[C]	Tmin_[C]	RHmean_[%]	RHmax_[%]	\
count	2192.000000	2192.000000	2192.000000	2192.000000	2192.000000	

mean	8.421905	14.193431	3.483485	79.962612	96.879106
std	7.913800	9.381580	7.164197	10.783647	4.063225
min	-12.955556	-9.800000	-19.400000	42.576389	62.000000
25%	1.740625	5.900000	-1.625000	72.666667	97.000000
50%	8.680208	14.400000	3.300000	80.861111	98.000000
75%	15.078299	21.600000	9.800000	88.385417	99.000000
max	25.029861	35.000000	17.800000	99.215278	100.000000

	RHmin_ [%]	wind_2m_ [m/s]	solar_ [MJ/m2d]	Precip_ [mm/d]	ETO_ [mm]
count	2192.000000	2192.000000	2192.000000	2192.000000	2192.000000
mean	53.704836	1.349244	11.673437	2.967153	1.837890
std	17.446168	0.541800	7.821675	6.809449	1.668232
min	11.000000	0.383333	0.610200	0.000000	-0.153171
25%	40.000000	0.986806	4.970550	0.000000	0.399060
50%	51.000000	1.311111	9.714300	0.000000	1.292689
75%	65.000000	1.625000	17.860650	2.800000	3.097603
max	99.000000	4.738889	30.405000	98.300000	6.955875

```
[4]: lysimeters_h = pd.read_csv("data\swfluxes_2015_2020.csv",
                                index_col=0, parse_dates=True) ["2018": "2020"]
lysimeters = lysimeters_h.resample("d").sum() # resample from hourly to daily
lysimeters.describe()
```

[4]:	ET-L2	ET-L0	P-L2	P-L0	Seep-L2 \
count	1096.000000	1096.000000	1096.000000	1096.000000	1096.000000
mean	1.695424	1.78995	2.845985	2.848431	1.335739
std	1.631746	1.71750	6.079860	6.087051	2.409260
min	0.000000	0.00000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
25%	0.380000	0.41000	0.050000	0.040000	0.000000
50%	1.040000	1.13000	0.270000	0.240000	0.430000
75%	2.810000	2.90500	2.762500	2.777500	1.662500
max	7.930000	9.39000	79.550000	81.840000	21.310000

	Seep-L0
count	1096.000000
mean	1.315392
std	2.595492
min	0.000000
25%	0.000000
50%	0.350000
75%	1.500000
max	20.010000

```
[5]: sensors_h = pd.read_csv("data\sensors_2015_2020.csv",
                                index_col=0, parse_dates=True) ["2018": "2020"]
sensors = sensors_h.resample("d").mean()
sensors.describe()
```

```
[5]:      SWC_10_L2    SWC_10_L0    SWC_30_L2    SWC_30_L0    SWC_50_L2  \
count  1096.000000  1096.000000  1096.000000  1096.000000  1096.000000
mean    38.421799    37.013688    35.911641    33.099601    32.811599
std      5.316941     5.790485     2.512298     3.372163     2.156441
min     24.504167    19.571250    28.565833    22.788333    26.055833
25%     34.713021    33.450417    34.172188    30.652917    31.367604
50%     38.874583    38.461875    36.275833    33.551250    33.388125
75%     42.395208    41.847500    37.809062    35.668542    34.415937
max     50.315833    46.256250    40.501250    40.889167    37.036250
```

```
      SWC_50_L0    WP_10_L2    WP_10_L0    WP_30_L2    WP_30_L0  \
count  1096.000000  1096.000000  1096.000000  1096.000000  1096.000000
mean    28.266814   -181.819181  -211.068961  -186.341207  -214.637771
std      3.831295   197.631693   229.244069   182.561694   211.479843
min     19.371250  -772.836667  -845.539583  -820.655417  -831.310833
25%     25.570000  -287.991146  -338.336979  -251.269583  -345.632500
50%     28.538333   -82.922708   -93.755625   -99.897500  -109.068125
75%     31.027083   -33.680417  -35.769583   -63.197917   -62.863646
max     36.728750    7.193333    0.000000    0.000000    0.000000
```

```
      WP_50_L2    WP_50_L0    WP_140_L2    WP_140_L0
count  1096.000000  1096.000000  1096.000000  1096.000000
mean   -185.777406  -219.889766   -98.116866  -105.834224
std    177.813570   204.381302    71.568291   73.883609
min   -802.100833  -818.312500  -287.484167  -292.153333
25%   -249.043229  -340.974271  -126.195729  -166.328750
50%   -100.537500  -111.207500   -55.965000   -55.977083
75%   -68.709167   -75.168125   -55.336250   -55.265833
max     0.000000    0.000000    0.472500   -3.795833
```

```
[6]: phenology = pd.read_csv("data\crop_phenology_2015_2020.csv",
                             index_col=0, parse_dates=True) ["2018": "2020"]
phenology = phenology.reindex(pd.date_range("2018-1-1", "2020-12-31"))
phenology.describe()
```

```
[6]:      LAI_fs_L2    LAI_fs_L0    LAI_mix_L2    LAI_mix_L0    ch_L2  \
count  1096.000000  1096.000000  1096.000000  1096.000000  1096.000000
mean    1.399521    1.367485    1.407446    1.384256    0.165681
std      1.122752    1.152141    1.183114    1.215588    0.123536
min      0.200000    0.200000    0.200000    0.200000    0.100000
25%      0.500000    0.500000    0.500000    0.500000    0.100000
50%      0.500000    0.500000    0.500000    0.500000    0.100000
75%      2.455422    2.513301    2.502986    2.408988    0.196875
max      4.145400    4.494600    3.963117    4.494600    0.842500
```

```
      ch_L0    fspec_raw_L2    fspec_raw_L0    accu_raw_L2    accu_raw_L0
count  1096.000000    35.000000    35.000000    64.000000    64.000000
```

mean	0.183333	2.714506	2.679201	2.537813	2.701354
std	0.149847	0.711692	0.843030	1.174852	1.267293
min	0.100000	1.369200	0.731500	0.193333	0.503333
25%	0.100000	2.208350	2.398500	1.567500	1.683333
50%	0.100000	2.682200	2.681100	2.723333	2.613333
75%	0.236170	3.162400	3.144050	3.730833	3.565833
max	0.922500	4.145400	4.494600	5.013333	5.373333

```
[7]: periods = pd.read_csv("data\\veg_err_period.csv",
                           index_col=0, parse_dates=True)["2018":"2020"]
periods.describe()
```

```
[7]:
```

	L2_error	L0_error	smai_L0	smai_L2	wstress_smai_L0	\
count	1096.000000	1096.000000	1096.000000	1096.000000	1096.000000	
mean	0.008212	0.017336	-0.146290	-0.109905	0.029197	
std	0.090287	0.130579	1.009471	1.051965	0.168435	
min	0.000000	0.000000	-3.233010	-3.185787	0.000000	
25%	0.000000	0.000000	-0.878715	-0.838260	0.000000	
50%	0.000000	0.000000	-0.011087	0.042592	0.000000	
75%	0.000000	0.000000	0.622733	0.684595	0.000000	
max	1.000000	1.000000	2.185548	1.811884	1.000000	

	wstress_smai_L2	veg_period
count	1096.000000	1096.000000
mean	0.035584	0.487226
std	0.185335	0.500065
min	0.000000	0.000000
25%	0.000000	0.000000
50%	0.000000	0.000000
75%	0.000000	1.000000
max	1.000000	1.000000

```
[8]: co2 = pd.read_csv("data\co2_levels_2018_2020.csv",
                       index_col=0, parse_dates=True)["2018":"2020"]
co2.describe()
```

```
[8]:
```

	L2	L0	flag	TAR_20	TAR_30
count	534.000000	534.000000	903.000000	472.000000	472.000000
mean	640.566840	418.270352	0.064230	0.685936	0.789642
std	98.005257	19.838111	0.245299	0.116074	0.105217
min	391.300077	374.711867	0.000000	0.349010	0.431746
25%	609.196900	404.140367	0.000000	0.617014	0.736689
50%	676.268531	415.792728	0.000000	0.698437	0.806111
75%	705.984001	431.000000	0.000000	0.770502	0.868088
max	794.713148	492.775903	1.000000	0.947080	0.978102

3 2. Simple statistics and plots of the analysed data

3.1 2.1 Meteorological data used for the analysis plot

```
[9]: # figure 2 in paper
fig2 = plot_figure2(lysimeters, meteo)
#fig2.savefig("figures\\figure2.png", dpi=300)
```

```
C:\matevz_work\notebooks\Vremec_co2_2022_JOH_zenodo\utils.py:249: UserWarning:
FixedFormatter should only be used together with FixedLocator
  axs[3].set_xticklabels(labels)
```


3.2 2.1 Annual change in soil water fluxes between L_{amb} and L_{eCO_2}

```
[10]: # Compute percentage change relative to ambient conditons (L0)
yearly_sum = lysimeters.resample("y").sum()
yearly_sum["P_avg"] = (yearly_sum["P-L2"] + yearly_sum["P-L0"]) / 2
yearly_sum["P_diff"] = ((yearly_sum["P-L2"] - yearly_sum["P-L0"]) /
    ↪yearly_sum["P-L0"] * 100)
yearly_sum["ET_avg"] = (yearly_sum["ET-L2"] + yearly_sum["ET-L0"]) / 2
yearly_sum["ET_diff"] = ((yearly_sum["ET-L2"] - yearly_sum["ET-L0"]) /
    ↪yearly_sum["ET-L0"] * 100)
yearly_sum["Seep_avg"] = (yearly_sum["Seep-L2"] + yearly_sum["Seep-L0"]) / 2
yearly_sum["Seep_diff"] = ((yearly_sum["Seep-L2"] - yearly_sum["Seep-L0"]) /
    ↪yearly_sum["Seep-L0"] * 100)
yearly_sum
```

```
[10]:          ET-L2    ET-L0    P-L2    P-L0    Seep-L2    Seep-L0    P_avg \
time
2018-12-31  667.555  719.865  1041.52  1072.66   381.46   383.89  1057.090
```

2019-12-31	563.050	595.960	989.00	1000.51	567.35	578.93	994.755
2020-12-31	627.580	645.960	1088.68	1048.71	515.16	478.85	1068.695

	P_diff	ET_avg	ET_diff	Seep_avg	Seep_diff
time					
2018-12-31	-2.903063	693.710	-7.266640	382.675	-0.632994
2019-12-31	-1.150413	579.505	-5.522183	573.140	-2.000242
2020-12-31	3.811349	636.770	-2.845377	497.005	7.582750

3.3 2.2 Change in soil water fluxes between the vegetation period L_{amb} and L_{eCO_2}

```
[11]: # Compute percentage change relative to ambient conditons (L0)
yearly_sum_veg = lysimeters[periods["veg_period"] == 1].resample("y").sum()
yearly_sum_veg["P_avg"] = (yearly_sum_veg["P-L2"] + yearly_sum_veg["P-L0"]) / 2
yearly_sum_veg["P_diff"] = yearly_sum_veg["P-L2"] - yearly_sum_veg["P-L0"]
yearly_sum_veg["P_diff%"] = ((yearly_sum_veg["P-L2"] - yearly_sum_veg["P-L0"]) /
    ↪ yearly_sum_veg["P-L0"] * 100)
yearly_sum_veg["ET_avg"] = (yearly_sum_veg["ET-L2"] + yearly_sum_veg["ET-L0"]) /
    ↪ 2
yearly_sum_veg["ET_diff"] = yearly_sum_veg["ET-L2"] - yearly_sum_veg["ET-L0"]
yearly_sum_veg["ET_diff%"] = ((yearly_sum_veg["ET-L2"] -
    ↪ yearly_sum_veg["ET-L0"]) / yearly_sum_veg["ET-L0"] * 100)
yearly_sum_veg["Seep_avg"] = (yearly_sum_veg["Seep-L2"] +
    ↪ yearly_sum_veg["Seep-L0"]) / 2
yearly_sum_veg["Seep_diff"] = yearly_sum_veg["Seep-L2"] -
    ↪ yearly_sum_veg["Seep-L0"]
yearly_sum_veg["Seep_diff%"] = ((yearly_sum_veg["Seep-L2"] -
    ↪ yearly_sum_veg["Seep-L0"]) / yearly_sum_veg["Seep-L0"] * 100)
yearly_sum_veg
```

```
[11]:
```

	ET-L2	ET-L0	P-L2	P-L0	Seep-L2	Seep-L0	P_avg \
time							
2018-12-31	546.935	590.075	481.20	479.35	5.86	5.59	480.275
2019-12-31	469.850	494.680	456.08	466.33	11.44	4.13	461.205
2020-12-31	501.570	517.350	638.62	620.43	175.83	144.52	629.525

	P_diff	P_diff%	ET_avg	ET_diff	ET_diff%	Seep_avg	Seep_diff \
time							
2018-12-31	1.85	0.385939	568.505	-43.14	-7.310935	5.725	0.27
2019-12-31	-10.25	-2.198014	482.265	-24.83	-5.019406	7.785	7.31
2020-12-31	18.19	2.931838	509.460	-15.78	-3.050159	160.175	31.31

	Seep_diff%
time	
2018-12-31	4.830054
2019-12-31	176.997579

2020-12-31 21.664821

```
[12]: # difference in P between wet and dry years for the vegetation period
print((yearly_sum_veg.loc["2018":"2019", "P_avg"].mean() - yearly_sum_veg.
      ↪loc["2020", "P_avg"].mean())
      / yearly_sum_veg.loc["2018":"2019", "P_avg"].mean() * 100)
```

-33.730934273696725

3.4 2.3 Changes in soil water fluxes between the start of the growing season and the end of the year

```
[13]: # Compute index for this period starting at the start of the growing season,
      ↪until the end of the year
idx_veg18s = periods[periods["veg_period"]==1].loc["2018"].index.union(pd.
      ↪date_range("2018-9-1", "2018-12-31"))
idx_veg19s = periods[periods["veg_period"]==1].loc["2019"].index.union(pd.
      ↪date_range("2019-9-1", "2019-12-31"))
idx_veg20s = periods[periods["veg_period"]==1].loc["2020"].index.union(pd.
      ↪date_range("2020-9-1", "2020-12-31"))
idx_vegs = idx_veg18s.union(idx_veg19s).union(idx_veg20s)
```

```
[14]: # Compute percentage change relative to ambient conditons (L0)
yearly_sum_vegs = lysimeters.loc[idx_vegs, :].resample("y").sum()
yearly_sum_vegs["Seep_avg"] = (yearly_sum_vegs["Seep-L2"] +
      ↪yearly_sum_vegs["Seep-L0"]) / 2
yearly_sum_vegs["Seep_diff"] = yearly_sum_vegs["Seep-L2"] -
      ↪yearly_sum_vegs["Seep-L0"]
yearly_sum_vegs["Seep_diff%"] = ((yearly_sum_vegs["Seep-L2"] -
      ↪yearly_sum_vegs["Seep-L0"]) / yearly_sum_vegs["Seep-L0"] * 100)
yearly_sum_vegs
```

```
[14]:
```

	ET-L2	ET-L0	P-L2	P-L0	Seep-L2	Seep-L0	Seep_avg	\
2018-12-31	591.525	638.565	811.06	842.55	158.43	168.22	163.325	
2019-12-31	507.890	539.060	810.93	817.46	279.53	252.68	266.105	
2020-12-31	565.230	585.130	840.11	825.99	318.31	284.32	301.315	

	Seep_diff	Seep_diff%
2018-12-31	-9.79	-5.819760
2019-12-31	26.85	10.626088
2020-12-31	33.99	11.954840

```
[15]: fig3 = plot_figure3(yearly_sum_veg)
      ↪fig3.savefig("figures\\figure3.png", dpi=300)
```



```
[16]: fig5 = plot_figure5(lysimeters, periods, phenology, co2, sensors)
#fig5.savefig("figures\figure5.png", dpi=300)
```


4 3 Effects of elevated CO_2 on ET and leaf area index (LAI)

4.1 3.1 Effects of elevated CO_2 on actual evapotranspiration

```
[17]: # include errors (measurement errors, manamegement, cuts, ...)
et_lysi_L0 = lysimeters["ET-L0"].copy()
et_lysi_L2 = lysimeters["ET-L2"].copy()
# Only analyse days with no errors, no water stress and inside the growing_
  ↳season
et_lysi_L0[(periods["L0_error"] == 1) | (periods["wstress_smai_L0"] == 1) |
  ↳(periods["veg_period"] == 0)] = np.nan
et_lysi_L2[(periods["L2_error"] == 1) | (periods["wstress_smai_L2"] == 1) |
  ↳(periods["veg_period"] == 0)] = np.nan

obs_L0 = et_lysi_L0.copy()
obs_L2 = et_lysi_L2.copy()
```

```

# Exclude days when L2=L0 and when co2 are the same
merror = et_lysi_L0[et_lysi_L0 == et_lysi_L2].index
obs_L0[merror] = np.nan
obs_L2[merror] = np.nan

# exclude days when co2 was not working
obs_L2[co2[co2["flag"] == 1].index] = np.nan
# days when co2 was operating and the CO2 difference was more than 240 ppm
idx2 = co2[co2["L2"] - co2["L0"] > 240].index # daily average co2_
↳ concentration higher than 240 ppm
idx2_1 = co2[co2["TAR_30"] > 0.7].index # achievement ratio higher than 0.7
# days when co2 difference was smaller than 40 ppm
idx = co2[co2["L2"] - co2["L0"] < 42].index

# leaf area index higher than 1.
lai_idL2 = phenology.loc[phenology["LAI_mix_L2"] > 1, "LAI_mix_L2"].index
lai_idL0 = phenology.loc[phenology["LAI_mix_L0"] > 1, "LAI_mix_L0"].index

# create errors series
idxL0_noerr = obs_L0[obs_L0.notnull()].index
idxL2_noerr = obs_L2[obs_L2.notnull()].index
# days when co2 was operating
idxL2_noerr = idxL2_noerr.intersection(idx2)
idxL2_noerr = idxL2_noerr.intersection(idx2_1)
# leaf area index higher than 1.
idxL2_noerr = idxL2_noerr.intersection(lai_idL2)
idxL0_noerr = idxL0_noerr.intersection(lai_idL0)
print(len(idxL2_noerr), len(idxL0_noerr))

```

217 370

```

[18]: fig4 = plot_figure4(lysimeters, idxL0_noerr, idxL2_noerr, idx)
#fig4.savefig("figures\\figure4.png", dpi=300)

```


4.2 3.2 Effects of elevated CO_2 on leaf area index

Assumptions of this parametric test: * Assumption 1: Are the two samples independent? * Assumption 2: Are the data from each of the 2 groups following a normal distribution? * Assumption 3: Do the two samples have the same variances (Homogeneity of Variance)?

```
[19]: s1, e1 = ("2018", "2020")
lai_accupar = pd.DataFrame({
    "L2": phenology.loc[s1:e1, "accu_raw_L2"],
    "L0": phenology.loc[s1:e1, "accu_raw_L0"],}).dropna()
lai_fspect = pd.DataFrame({
    "L2": phenology.loc[s1:e1, "fspec_raw_L2"],
    "L0": phenology.loc[s1:e1, "fspec_raw_L0"],}).dropna()
```

```
[20]: # 2. Are the data from each of the 2 groups following a normal distribution?
plt.hist(lai_fspect["L2"], bins=20);
```



```
[21]: plt.hist(lai_fspect["L0"], bins=10);
```



```
[22]: # check ACCUPAR/fieldspec LAI
figapp1 = plot_appendix1(lai_accupar, lai_fspec)
#figapp1.savefig("figures\appendix_1.png", dpi=300)
```


5 4. Estimate stomatal resistance (r_l) for each lysimeter

The analysis included days when:

1. No measurement errors
2. No water stress was observed
3. Only between the start of the growing period and last cut of the year
4. $LAI > 1$, to reduce the effect of soil evaporation

additionally, $LAI - eCO_2$ excluded days when:

5. FACE was not operating (daily CO_2 must be higher than 230 ppm)

```
[23]: # create def for potential evaporation estimation
lat = 47.4935 * np.pi / 180 # 47.4935° N
def et_sc1(r_l, lai, croph, noerrors):
    pe = pyet.pm(
        meteo.loc["2018":, "Tmean_[C]"],
        meteo.loc["2018":, "wind_2m_[m/s]"],
        rs=meteo.loc["2018":, "solar_[MJ/m2d]"],
        elevation=700,
        lat=lat,
        rhmax=meteo.loc["2018":, "RHmax_[%]"],
        rhmin=meteo.loc["2018":, "RHmin_[%]"],
        tmax=meteo.loc["2018":, "Tmax_[C]"],
        tmin=meteo.loc["2018":, "Tmin_[C]"],
        lai=lai,
        croph=croph,
        r_l=r_l,
        a=1,
        b=0,
        ra_method=2,
        lai_eff=0,
    )
    return pe[noerrors]
```

```
[24]: model = Model(et_sc1, independent_vars=["lai", "croph", "noerrors"])
parameters = Parameters()
parameters.add("r_l", value=100, min=20, max=160)
res_L0_sc1 = model.fit(
    et_lysi_L0[idxL0_noerr],
    lai=phenology.loc[idxL0_noerr, "LAI_mix_L0"],
    croph=phenology.loc[idxL0_noerr, "ch_L0"],
    noerrors=idxL0_noerr,
    params=parameters,
    method="least_squares",
)
res_L2_sc1 = model.fit(
    et_lysi_L2[idxL2_noerr],
    lai=phenology.loc[idxL2_noerr, "LAI_mix_L2"],
    croph=phenology.loc[idxL2_noerr, "ch_L2"],
    noerrors=idxL2_noerr,
    params=parameters,
    method="least_squares",
)
```

```
[25]: print(durbin_watson(res_L0_sc1.residual))
print(durbin_watson(res_L2_sc1.residual))
```

```
1.2488875635965795
1.2194801957433241
```

- low Durbin -> autocorrelation

5.1 3.5 Estimate r_l for each lysimeter using AR(1) model

- autocorrelation needs to be removed from the residuals.
- An autoregressive model of order 1 (AR(1)) is used to do that.

```
[26]: def residuals(pars, lai, croph, obs, idx_noerror):
    params = pars.valuesdict()
    r_l = params["r_l"]
    alpha = params["alpha"]
    pe = pyet.pmet(
        meteo.loc["2018":, "Tmean_[C]"],
        meteo.loc["2018":, "wind_2m_[m/s]"],
        rs=meteo.loc["2018":, "solar_[MJ/m2d]"],
        elevation=700,
        lat=lat,
        rhmax=meteo.loc["2018":, "RHmax_[%]"],
        rhmin=meteo.loc["2018":, "RHmin_[%]"],
        tmax=meteo.loc["2018":, "Tmax_[C]"],
        tmin=meteo.loc["2018":, "Tmin_[C]"],
        lai=lai,
        croph=croph,
        r_l=r_l,
        a=1,
        b=0,
        ra_method=2,
        lai_eff=0,
    )
    resid = (pe - obs).dropna()
    noise = pd.Series(index=resid.index, dtype="float64", name="Noise")
    noise.iloc[0] = resid.values[0]
    noise.iloc[1:] = resid[1:].values - alpha * resid[:-1].values
    return noise[idx_noerror]
```

```
[27]: params = Parameters()
params.add("r_l", value=100, min=10, max=160)
params.add("alpha", value=0.8, min=1e-5, max=5000)
rl_model_L0 = Minimizer(
    residuals,
    params,
    fcn_args=(phenology.loc["2018":, "LAI_mix_L0"], phenology.loc["2018":,
    ↪ "ch_L0"]),
    fcn_kws={"obs": lysimeters["ET-L0"]["2018":], "idx_noerror": idxL0_noerr},
)
rl_model_L2 = Minimizer(
    residuals,
    params,
```

```

    fcn_args=(phenology.loc["2018":, "LAI_mix_L2"], phenology.loc["2018":,
↪ "ch_L2"]),
    fcn_kws={"obs": lysimeters["ET-L2"]["2018":], "idx_noerror": idxL2_noerr},
)

```

```

[28]: rl_result_L0 = rl_model_L0.minimize(method="least_squares")
      rl_result_L2 = rl_model_L2.minimize(method="least_squares")

```

```

[29]: rl_L0_auto = rl_result_L0.params["r_1"].value
      rl_L2_auto = rl_result_L2.params["r_1"].value
      print("rl_L0 = {}, rl_c2 = {}".format(rl_L0_auto, rl_L2_auto))

```

rl_L0 = 78.34549450197846, rl_c2 = 118.00701185220365

```

[30]: # error propagation
      ((4+6.7)/(rl_L2_auto - rl_L0_auto)+ (4/rl_L0_auto))*((rl_L2_auto - rl_L0_auto) /
↪ rl_L0_auto)*100

```

[30]: 16.24210132294915

```

[31]: # 95 % confidence intervals
      ci_L0 = conf_interval(rl_model_L0, rl_result_L0, p_names=["r_1"])
      printfuncs.report_ci(ci_L0)

```

	99.73%	95.45%	68.27%	_BEST_	68.27%	95.45%	99.73%
r_1:	-11.68180	-7.82572	-3.94188	78.34549	+4.03941	+8.21552	+12.57476

```

[32]: # 95 % confidence intervals
      ci_L2 = conf_interval(rl_model_L2, rl_result_L2, p_names=["r_1"])
      printfuncs.report_ci(ci_L2)

```

	99.73%	95.45%	68.27%	_BEST_	68.27%	95.45%	99.73%
r_1:	-20.09035	-13.33564	-6.68143	118.00701	+6.83150	+13.93912	+21.46539

```

[33]: rl_L0_auto = rl_result_L0.params["r_1"].value
      rl_L2_auto = rl_result_L2.params["r_1"].value
      print("rl_L0 = {}, rl_c2 = {}".format(rl_L0_auto, rl_L2_auto))
      print("% Increase in stomatal resistance = {} +-{} / {}%".format(round(100 *
↪ (rl_L2_auto - rl_L0_auto) / rl_L0_auto,0),
                                                                    round(100*
↪ ((ci_L2["r_1"][1][1]) - ci_L0["r_1"][5][1]) / ci_L0["r_1"][5][1],0),
                                                                    round(100*
↪ ((ci_L2["r_1"][1][1]) - ci_L0["r_1"][5][1]) / ci_L0["r_1"][5][1],0)))

```

rl_L0 = 78.34549450197846, rl_c2 = 118.00701185220365
% Increase in stomatal resistance = 51.0 +-21.0/21.0%

```

[34]: print(durbin_watson(rl_result_L0.residual))
      print(durbin_watson(rl_result_L2.residual))

```

```
print("Durbin-Wattson > 1.5 is acceptable.")
```

```
1.830823284015286
```

```
1.7019582496055419
```

```
Durbin-Wattson > 1.5 is acceptable.
```

```
[35]: pe_L0_cal = et_sc1(rl_L0_auto, phenology["LAI_mix_L0"], phenology["ch_L0"],  
      ↪noerrors=idxL0_noerr)  
      pe_L2_cal = et_sc1(rl_L2_auto, phenology["LAI_mix_L2"], phenology["ch_L2"],  
      ↪noerrors=idxL2_noerr)
```

```
[36]: pe_1 = et_sc1(66, 1, 0.2, noerrors=pd.date_range("2018-1-1", "2020-12-31"))  
      pe_2 = et_sc1(74.4, 1, 0.2, noerrors=pd.date_range("2018-1-1", "2020-12-31"))
```

```
[37]: (pe_2.resample("y").sum()-pe_1.resample("y").sum())/pe_1.resample("y").sum() *  
      ↪100
```

```
[37]: 2018-12-31    -3.669323  
      2019-12-31    -3.692774  
      2020-12-31    -3.731042  
      Freq: A-DEC, dtype: float64
```

```
[38]: fig6 = plot_figure6(pe_L0_cal, pe_L2_cal, obs_L0, obs_L2, rl_L0_auto,  
      ↪rl_L2_auto, ci_L0, ci_L2)  
      #fig6.savefig("figures\\figure6.png", dpi=300)
```


6 5. Calibrate/parameterize the stomatal resistance model

```
[39]: def residuals_co2(pars, tmean, obs, idx_noerror):  
      params = pars.valuesdict()  
      r_l = params["r_l"]  
      srl = params["srl"]  
      alpha = params["alpha"]  
      pe_L2 = pyet.pm(  
          meteo.loc["2018":, "Tmean_[C]"],  
          meteo.loc["2018":, "wind_2m_[m/s]"],  
          rs=meteo.loc["2018":, "solar_[MJ/m2d]"],
```

```

elevation=700,
lat=lat,
rhmax=meteo.loc["2018":, "RHmax_[%]"],
rhmin=meteo.loc["2018":, "RHmin_[%]"],
tmax=meteo.loc["2018":, "Tmax_[C]"],
tmin=meteo.loc["2018":, "Tmin_[C]"],
lai=phenology.loc["2016-7":, "LAI_mix_L2"],
croph=phenology.loc["2016-7":, "ch_L2"],
srs=srl,
r_l=r_l,
a=1,
b=0,
ra_method=2,
lai_eff=0,
co2=co2.loc["2018":, "L2"],
)
pe_L0 = pyet.pm(
    meteo.loc["2018":, "Tmean_[C]"],
    meteo.loc["2018":, "wind_2m_[m/s]"],
    rs=meteo.loc["2018":, "solar_[MJ/m2d]"],
    elevation=700,
    lat=lat,
    rhmax=meteo.loc["2018":, "RHmax_[%]"],
    rhmin=meteo.loc["2018":, "RHmin_[%]"],
    tmax=meteo.loc["2018":, "Tmax_[C]"],
    tmin=meteo.loc["2018":, "Tmin_[C]"],
    lai=phenology.loc["2016-7":, "LAI_mix_L0"],
    croph=phenology.loc["2016-7":, "ch_L0"],
    srs=srl,
    r_l=r_l,
    a=1,
    b=0,
    ra_method=2,
    lai_eff=0,
    co2=co2.loc["2018":, "L0"],
)
resid1 = pe_L2 - obs[0]
noise1 = pd.Series(index=resid1.index, dtype="float64", name="Noise")
noise1.iloc[0] = resid1.values[0]
noise1.iloc[1:] = resid1[1:].values - alpha * resid1[:-1].values
noise1 = noise1[idx_noerror[0]].dropna()
resid2 = pe_L0 - obs[1]
noise2 = pd.Series(index=resid2.index, dtype="float64", name="Noise")
noise2.iloc[0] = resid2.values[0]
noise2.iloc[1:] = resid2[1:].values - alpha * resid2[:-1].values
noise2 = noise2[idx_noerror[1]].dropna()
return np.concatenate((noise1.values, noise2.values))

```

```
[40]: # include errors
obs_srl = [lysimeters["ET-L2"]["2018:"].copy(), lysimeters["ET-L0"]["2018:"].
↳copy()]
noerror = [idxL2_noerr, idxL0_noerr]
```

```
[41]: params = Parameters()
params.add("r_l", value=55, min=10, max=210)
params.add("srl", value=0.0009, min=0.01, max=0.001)
params.add("alpha", value=0.3, min=1e-5, max=5000)
srl_model = Minimizer(
    residuals_co2,
    params,
    fcn_args=(meteo.loc["2018:", "Tmean_[C]"),),
    fcn_kws={"obs": obs_srl, "idx_noerror": noerror},)
srl_result = srl_model.minimize(method="least_squares")
```

```
[42]: ci = conf_interval(srl_model, srl_result, p_names=["r_l", "srl"])
printfuncs.report_ci(ci)
```

```
C:\Users\Matevz\anaconda3\lib\site-packages\lmfit\confidence.py:319:
UserWarning: Bound reached with prob(srl=0.001) = 0.9593023547149254 <
max(sigmas)
warn(errmsg)
```

	99.73%	95.45%	68.27%	_BEST_	68.27%	95.45%	99.73%
r_l:	-17.09283	-11.42002	-5.73287	64.59073	+5.81008	+11.73407	+16.99859
srl:	-inf	-0.00102	-0.00055	0.00204	+0.00065	+0.00144	+0.00243

```
[43]: print(ci["r_l"][1][1], ci["r_l"][5][1])
print(ci["srl"][1][1], ci["srl"][5][1])
```

```
53.17071638845674 76.32480916467628
0.0010203555097886548 0.003485007321391363
```

```
[44]: res_rl_300_auto = srl_result.params["r_l"].value
res_srl_auto = srl_result.params["srl"].value
print(res_rl_300_auto)
print(res_srl_auto)
```

```
64.59073424943304
0.0020414178667396
```

6.1 Estimate rl for each year

```
[45]: def residuals3(pars, tmean, obs):
    params = pars.valuesdict()
    r_l = params["r_l"]
    srl = params["srl"]
    alpha = params["alpha"]
```

```

pe_L2 = pyet.pm(
    tmean,
    meteo.loc["2016-7":, "u2 [m/s]"],
    rs=meteo.loc["2016-7":, "Rs [MJ/m2d]"],
    elevation=700,
    lat=lat2,
    rhmax=meteo.loc["2016-7":, "rh_max [%]"],
    rhmin=meteo.loc["2016-7":, "rh_min [%]"],
    tmax=meteo.loc["2016-7":, "Tmax [C]"],
    tmin=meteo.loc["2016-7":, "Tmin [C]"],
    lai=phenology.loc["2016-7":, "LAI_L2"],
    croph=phenology.loc["2016-7":, "ch_L2"],
    ra_method=2,
    a=1,
    b=0,
    lai_eff=0,
    co2=co2.loc["2016-7":, "L2"],
    r_l=r_l,
    srs=srl,
)
pe_L0 = pyet.pm(
    tmean,
    meteo.loc["2016-7":, "u2 [m/s]"],
    rs=meteo.loc["2016-7":, "Rs [MJ/m2d]"],
    elevation=700,
    lat=lat2,
    rhmax=meteo.loc["2016-7":, "rh_max [%]"],
    rhmin=meteo.loc["2016-7":, "rh_min [%]"],
    tmax=meteo.loc["2016-7":, "Tmax [C]"],
    tmin=meteo.loc["2016-7":, "Tmin [C]"],
    lai=phenology.loc["2016-7":, "LAI_L0"],
    croph=phenology.loc["2016-7":, "ch_L0"],
    ra_method=2,
    a=1,
    b=0,
    lai_eff=0,
    co2=co2.loc["2016-7":, "L0"].copy(),
    r_l=r_l,
    srs=srl,
)
pe_L2 = pe_L2[obs_c2_co2.dropna().index]
resid1 = np.array(pe_L2 - obs[0])
noise1 = np.append(resid1[0], resid1[1:] - resid1[:-1] * np.exp(-1 / alpha))

pe_L0 = pe_L0[obs_c0_co2.dropna().index]
resid2 = np.array(pe_L0 - obs[1])
noise2 = np.append(resid2[0], resid2[1:] - resid2[:-1] * np.exp(-1 / alpha))

```

```
return np.concatenate((noise1, noise2))
```

```
[46]: params = Parameters()
params.add("r_1", value=100, min=10, max=160)
params.add("alpha", value=0.3, min=1e-5, max=5000)
rls_L0 = []
rls_L0_std = []
rls_L2 = []
rls_L2_std = []
co2s_L0 = []
co2s_L2 = []
year = "2018"
res_auto_L0 = minimize(
    residuals,
    params,
    args=(phenology.loc[year, "LAI_mix_L0"], phenology.loc[year, "ch_L0"]),
    kws={"obs": lysimeters.loc[year, "ET-L0"],
        "idx_noerror": lysimeters.loc[idxL0_noerr].loc[year].index,},
    method="least_squares",)
res_auto_L2 = minimize(
    residuals,
    params,
    args=(phenology.loc[year, "LAI_mix_L2"], phenology.loc[year, "ch_L2"]),
    kws={"obs": lysimeters.loc[year, "ET-L2"],
        "idx_noerror": lysimeters.loc[idxL2_noerr].loc[year].index,},
    method="least_squares",
)
rls_L0.append(res_auto_L0.params["r_1"].value)
rls_L2.append(res_auto_L2.params["r_1"].value)
co2s_L0.append(co2.loc[idxL0_noerr[idxL0_noerr.year == int(year)], "L0"].mean())
co2s_L2.append(co2.loc[idxL2_noerr[idxL2_noerr.year == int(year)], "L2"].mean())
rls_L0_std.append(res_auto_L0.params["r_1"].stderr)
rls_L2_std.append(res_auto_L2.params["r_1"].stderr);
```

```
[47]: for year in ("2019", "2020"):
    res_auto_L0 = minimize(
        residuals,
        params,
        args=(phenology.loc[year, "LAI_mix_L0"], phenology.loc[year, "ch_L0"]),
        kws={"obs": lysimeters.loc[year, "ET-L0"],
            "idx_noerror": lysimeters.loc[idxL0_noerr].loc[year].index,},
        method="least_squares",)
    res_auto_L2 = minimize(
        residuals,
        params,
        args=(phenology.loc[year, "LAI_mix_L2"], phenology.loc[year, "ch_L2"]),
        kws={"obs": lysimeters.loc[year, "ET-L2"],
```

```

        "idx_noerror": lysimeters.loc[idxL2_noerr].loc[year].index,},
        method="least_squares",)
    rls_L0.append(res_auto_L0.params["r_1"].value)
    rls_L2.append(res_auto_L2.params["r_1"].value)
    co2s_L0.append(co2.loc[idxL0_noerr[idxL0_noerr.year == int(year)], "L0"].
↳mean())
    co2s_L2.append(co2.loc[idxL2_noerr[idxL2_noerr.year == int(year)], "L2"].
↳mean())
    rls_L0_std.append(res_auto_L0.params["r_1"].stderr)
    rls_L2_std.append(res_auto_L2.params["r_1"].stderr)

```

```

[48]: co2_pre2005 = pd.read_csv("C://matevz_work//notebooks//co2_paper_2018_2020//
↳data//rcp\PRE2005_MIDYR_CONC.DAT",
                                skiprows=38, delim_whitespace=True,
↳index_col="YEARS",).loc[:, "CO2"]
co2_rcp3 = pd.read_csv("C://matevz_work//notebooks//co2_paper_2018_2020//data//
↳rcp\RCP3PD_MIDYR_CONC.DAT",
                                skiprows=38, delim_whitespace=True, index_col="YEARS",).
↳loc[:, "CO2"]
co2_rcp45 = pd.read_csv("C://matevz_work//notebooks//co2_paper_2018_2020//data//
↳rcp\RCP45_MIDYR_CONC.DAT",
                                skiprows=38, delim_whitespace=True, index_col="YEARS",).
↳loc[:, "CO2"]
co2_rcp6 = pd.read_csv("C://matevz_work//notebooks//co2_paper_2018_2020//data//
↳rcp\RCP6_MIDYR_CONC.DAT",
                                skiprows=38, delim_whitespace=True, index_col="YEARS",).
↳loc[:, "CO2"]
co2_rcp85 = pd.read_csv("C://matevz_work//notebooks//co2_paper_2018_2020//data//
↳rcp\RCP85_MIDYR_CONC.DAT",
                                skiprows=38, delim_whitespace=True, index_col="YEARS",).
↳loc[:, "CO2"]

```

```

[49]: # CO2 concentration at the year of 2100

```

```

print(co2_rcp3[2100])
print(co2_rcp45[2100])
print(co2_rcp6[2100])
print(co2_rcp85[2100])

```

```

420.89546
538.3583
669.72317
935.87437

```

```

[50]: rl_pre2005 = res_rl_300_auto * (1 + res_srl_auto * (co2_pre2005 - 300))
rl_rcp3 = res_rl_300_auto * (1 + res_srl_auto * (co2_rcp3 - 300))
rl_rcp45 = res_rl_300_auto * (1 + res_srl_auto * (co2_rcp45 - 300))
rl_rcp6 = res_rl_300_auto * (1 + res_srl_auto * (co2_rcp6 - 300))

```

```
rl_rcp85 = res_rl_300_auto * (1 + res_srl_auto * (co2_rcp85 - 300))
```

```
[51]: fig7 = plot_figure7(res_rl_300_auto, res_srl_auto, co2s_L0,
                        rls_L0, rls_L0_std, co2_rcp3, co2_rcp45,
                        co2_rcp6, co2_rcp85, co2_pre2005, co2,
                        ci, co2s_L2, rls_L2, rls_L2_std,
                        idxL0_noerr, idxL2_noerr,
                        rl_L0_auto, rl_L2_auto,)
#fig7.savefig("figures\\figure7.png", dpi=300)
```


co₂ stomatal resistance model and the 95 % confidence interval

7 6. Water stress.

```
[52]: def et_sc2(r_l, lai, croph, s1="2018"):
    pe = pyet.pm(
        meteo.loc[s1:, "Tmean_[C]"],
        meteo.loc[s1:, "wind_2m_[m/s]"],
        rs=meteo.loc[s1:, "solar_[MJ/m2d]"],
        elevation=700,
        lat=lat,
        rhmax=meteo.loc[s1:, "RHmax_[%]"],
        rhmin=meteo.loc[s1:, "RHmin_[%]"],
        tmax=meteo.loc[s1:, "Tmax_[C]"],
        tmin=meteo.loc[s1:, "Tmin_[C]"],
        lai=lai,
        croph=croph,
        r_l=r_l,
        a=1,
        b=0,
        lai_eff=0,
        ra_method=2,
    )
    return pe
```

```
[53]: pe_L0 = et_sc2(100, phenology["LAI_mix_L0"], phenology["ch_L0"])
      pe_L2 = et_sc2(100, phenology["LAI_mix_L2"], phenology["ch_L2"])
```

```
[54]: # edit default values for plots
      params = {"lines.linewidth": "0.4"}
      pylab.rcParams.update(params)
```

```
[55]: swc_L0 = sensors["SWC_30_L0"].resample("d").mean()
      swc_L2 = sensors["SWC_30_L2"].resample("d").mean()
      smai_L0 = (swc_L0 - swc_L0.mean()) / swc_L0.std()
      smai_L2 = (swc_L2 - swc_L2.mean()) / swc_L2.std()

      obs_L0_smai = lysimeters.loc["2018":"2020", "ET-L0"]
      obs_L2_smai = lysimeters.loc["2018":"2020", "ET-L2"]

      figapp2 = plot_appendix2(smai_L0, smai_L2, obs_L0_smai, obs_L2_smai, pe_L0,
      ↪pe_L2)
      #figapp2.savefig("figures\\appendix_2.png", dpi=300)
```

